

Tabernacle, The

also known as “Tent of Meeting, The”

By Brian DonnellyLewis, University of California - Los Angeles

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The Tabernacle (Heb. mishkan), also referred to as the Tent of Meeting (Heb. 'ohel mo'ed), was an ancient cultic tent dedicated to the worship of Yahweh described in the Hebrew Bible. According to the biblical text, the Tabernacle facilitated the worship of Yahweh during the Israelite sojourn from Egypt down to the early monarchic period in the southern Levant. As a movable cultic tent, the Tabernacle is said to have been brought by the Israelites from Mt. Sinai, where Israel's patron god Yahweh commanded its construction, through the 'wilderness wanderings,' into modern Israel/Palestine via the crossing of the Jordan River, until it finally came to rest at Shiloh (modern Tel Shiloh/Khirbet Seilun). Prior to the narration of its journey, the Tabernacle's construction is described in detail in the book of Exodus (25-31 and 35-40). Based on this text, the dimensions of the Tabernacle are estimated to be about 30 cubits in length and 10 cubits in width. The rectangular Tabernacle tent was the central piece of a much larger sacred complex enclosed by a perimeter fence measuring about 100 cubits in length and 50 cubits in width. In the fenced courtyard area of the complex stood a sacrificial altar and a large basin for ritual washing, with the entrance to the Tabernacle nearby. The Tabernacle consisted of two rooms, an entrance room which housed the menorah (a seven branched lamp), the table of showbread, and the incense altar. The entrance room was separated from the innermost room, called the Holy of Holies, by a decorated veil. Inside the Holy of Holies stood the ark of the covenant, and in the biblical tradition, the Holy of Holies was the dwelling place of the glory of Yahweh. In spite of its important in the biblical narrative, many modern scholars view the Tabernacle as an invented or imagined cultic space rather than a real historical cultic tent. This is due, in part, to the elaborate and expensive materials needed for its construction, as described in the book of Exodus. In this view, the Tabernacle represents a fictionalized or idealized cultic space which has been retrojected into antiquity by much later group of writers during or after the Judean's exile to Babylonia. There are many others, however, who argue for the historicity, however limited, of a cultic tent structure like the Tabernacle within the cultus of ancient Israel. In this view, the descriptions in Exodus may represent later embellishments, but the existence of analogous cultic tents from Near Eastern religious traditions, both contemporary to and predating the biblical tradition, suggests that the biblical Tabernacle is based on a historical reality. But whether real or imagined, the Tabernacle as presented in the Hebrew Bible represents the primary cultic site for the sacrificial cult of Yahweh prior to the construction of the Solomon temple in Jerusalem.

Date Range: 1200 BCE - 1000 BCE

Region: Tel Shiloh/Khirbet Seilun

Region tags: Israel, Palestine

The site of ancient Shiloh.

Status of Participants:

✓ Religious Specialists

General Variables

Sources and Excavations

Has this place been the focus of excavation (pre-modern, illicit, or scientific):

Answer 'Yes' for each period or type of excavation.

– Yes

↳ Type of excavation:

– Scientific

Notes: Extensive excavations have been conducted at the site of Shiloh (Tel Shiloh/Khirbet Seilun), though evidence related to the 'Tabernacle,' if it indeed existed, is not forthcoming and unlikely to be discovered due to the impermanence of its materials and its mobile nature.

↳ Years of excavation:

– Year range: 1981-1984

Notes: Excavations by Tel Aviv University

Reference: Israel Finkelstein , Shlomo Bunimovitz , Zvi Lederman , Salo Hellwing , Moshe Sadeh. Excavations at Shiloh 1981-1984: Preliminary Report.. Tel Aviv, 12(2)

Reference: Israel Finkelstein. Shiloh, 1982.

Reference: Israel Finkelstein. Shiloh, 1981.

– Year range: 1926-1932 and 1963

Notes: The "Danish" Excavations

Reference: Fleming Andersen G.. Shiloh II. The Danish Excavations at Tall Sailun, Palestine in 1926, 1929, 1932, and 1963: The Remains from the Hellenistic to the Mamluk Periods.. Denmark: Aarhus University Press.

Reference: Marie-Louise Buhl , Svend Homl-Nielson. Shiloh, The Pre-Hellenistic Remains: The Danish Excavations at Tell Sailun, Palestine, in 1926, 1929, 1932, and 1963.. Copenhagen: National Museum of Denmark and Aarhus University Press.

– Year range: 2017-Present

↳ Name of excavation

– Official or descriptive name: The Danish Excavations at Tall Sailun/Excavations at Shiloh

Topographical Context

Is the place associated with a feature in the landscape

– Other [specify]: The Place is Mobile and therefore unassociated with physical features in the landscape

Does the place involve human-made features besides structure:

Other features might be ground clearing, terracing, other modifications of the local environment.

– No

Is the place situated in an urban or significantly urbanized area:

– No

Is the place situated in a rural setting:

– Yes

↳ Are there settlements in close proximity to the place:

– Yes

↳ Are there routes of travel in close proximity to the place:

– Yes

Is the place situated far removed from non-religious places of habitation:

– I don't know

Structures Present

Are there structures or features present:

Instructions: Answer once for each structure/feature or group that can be differentiated.

– No

Reasons for Creation/Construction/Consecration

Is the place used for the worship of/communication with non-human supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Dedicated to a supernatural being:

– Yes [specify]: YHWH

↳ Dedicated to more than one supernatural being:

– No

Is the place used for the worship of a semi-divine human being:

– No

Is the place used for the worship of non-divine ancestors:

– No

Was the place commissioned/built by an official political entity:

A political entity is a local power structure that leverages a workforce.

– Field doesn't know

Were the Structures built by specific groups of people:

– Yes

Groups:

– Specialized labourers/craftspeople

Notes: According to the Biblical Tradition (Exod. 31).

Was the place thought to have originated as the result of divine intervention:

– Yes

Specify

– Revealed by high god

Was the place created to mark or commemorate the birthplace of a supernatural or human being:

– No

Was the place created as the result of an event:

– Yes

Specify

– Other [specify]: Revelation of Yahweh at Sinai

Was the creation of the place sponsored by an external financial/material donation:

– Yes

Is this sponsor of the same religious group/tradition as the main usage of the place:

– Yes

Notes: According to the book of Exodus, the Tabernacle is created from the materials donated by the people of Israel to Moses (Exod. 25:1-9).

Was the establishment of the place motivated by:

– Other [specify]: Divine Direction

Was the place built specifically for housing scriptures/sacred texts:

– No

Notes: According to the book of Exodus, the tablets of the covenant were said to be stored in the ark of the covenant, but this should not be considered the impetus for the construction of the religious space.

Design and Material Remains

Overall Structure

Is the place made up of multiple built structures:

– No

Is monumental architecture present:

Monumental architecture is defined here as a built structure that surpasses average human proportions and in general is larger and more complex than is necessary to fulfill the structure's utilitarian function(s). Examples of monumental architecture include Mesopotamian Ziggurats, Egyptian Pyramids, Greek and Roman temples, Mesoamerican Pyramids, North American and Aegean burial mounds, etc.

– No

Is the structure/feature made out of natural materials:

Answer [Yes] for each material type

– Yes

↳ Earth

– No

↳ Sand

– No

↳ Clay

– No

↳ Plaster

– No

↳ Wood
– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:
– Field doesn't know

↳ Grass
– No

↳ Stone
– No

Is the structure/feature made out of human-made materials

– Yes [specify]: linens

Decoration

Is decoration present:

– Yes

↳ Is decoration part of the building (permanent):
– Yes

↳ On the outside:
– No

↳ On the inside:
– Yes

↳ Is decoration attached to the building, i.e. movable reliefs or tapestries
– Yes

↳ Is the decoration figural:

A figural representation is defined here as one that contains the depiction of discernible human, anthropomorphic, animal, or zoomorphic forms. In general, it differentiates between animate and inanimate beings, as well as between narrative compositions and still life, landscapes, abstraction, etc. Answer [Yes] for each type of figure depicted

– Yes

↳ Are there gods depicted:

– No

↳ Are there other supernatural beings depicted:

– Yes

↳ Are there humans depicted:

– No

↳ Are there animals depicted:

– No

↳ Are there animal-human hybrids depicted:

– I don't know

Notes: Cherubim are supernatural beings (see above question) and were likely hybrid beings, of what sort I do not know.

↳ Is the decoration hidden or restricted from view:

– Yes

↳ Can the decoration be revealed:

– Yes

Notes: It is on the inner veil.

↳ Are there statues present:

– No

↳ Are there reliefs present:

A relief as opposed to sculpture carved on the round is a work of sculpture in which the figures project from a background support, generally a flat surface. Reliefs can be carved out of stone, clay, or a similar material.

– No

↳ Are there paintings present:

– No

↳ Are there mosaics present:

– No

↳ Are there inscriptions as part of the decoration:

– No

Iconography

Are there distinct features in the places iconography:

– Yes

↳ Eyes (stylized or not)

– No

↳ Supernatural beings (zoomorphic)

– Yes

Notes: Cherubim

↳ Supernatural beings (geomorphic)

– No

↳ Supernatural beings (anthropomorphic)

– I don't know

↳ Supernatural beings (abstract)

– No

↳ Portrayals of afterlife

– No

↳ Aspects of doctrine (e.g. cross, trinity, Mithraic symbols)

– I don't know

↳ Humans

– No

↳ Supernatural narratives

– No

Human narratives

– No

Beliefs and Practices

Funerary Associations

Is this place a tomb/burial:

– No

Is this a place for the worship of the dead:

– No

Is this a place for treatment of the corpse:

– No

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

Co-sacrifices are animal/human sacrifices prompted by the death of the primary occupant of the tomb/burial.

– No

Are grave goods present:

– No

Are formal burials present:

– No

Supernatural Beings

Is a supreme high god is present:

– Yes

Are they anthropomorphic:

– No

↳ Are they sky deity:

– I don't know

↳ Are they chthonic (underworld)

– No

↳ Are they fused with king/kingship role (king = high god)

– No

↳ Are they the monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god:

– No

↳ Are they kin relation to elites:

– No

↳ Are they other type of loyalty or connection to elites:

– Yes

↳ Are they unquestionably good:

– Yes

Does the supreme high god communicate with the living at this place:

– I don't know

Are previously human spirits present:

– No

Do human spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Are nonhuman supernatural beings present:

– No

Do nonhuman spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Are mixed human-divine beings present:

– No

Do mixed human-divine beings communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Is the supernatural being/high god present in the form of a cult statue(s):

– No

Supernatural Interactions

Is supernatural monitoring present:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural monitoring of norm adherence:

– Yes

Notes: Norm adherence of cultic practice.

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect offerings:

– Yes

↳ Libations:

– I don't know

↳ Offerings of food:

– I don't know

↳ Animal sacrifice:

– Yes [specify]: Bulls, Goats, Lambs, Doves, and Pigeons

↳ Human sacrifice:

– No

↳ Sacred objects:

– No

↳ Daily life objects:

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about sex:

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect proper ritual observance:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect performance of rituals:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect maintenance of the place:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect personal hygiene:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about honoring oaths:

– Yes

Do visitors communicate with the gods or supernatural beings:

– No

Ritual and Performance

Sacrifices, Offerings, and Maintenance

Are sacrifices performed at this place:

– Yes

↳ Are there animal sacrifices:

– Yes [specify]: Bulls, Goats, Lambs, Doves, and Pigeons.

↳ Are there human sacrifices:

– No

↳ Are the sacrificed humans associated in some way:

– No

Are there self-sacrifices present:

– No

Are material offerings present:

– No

Is attendance to worship/sacrifice mandatory:

– Yes

↳ By all the community

– Yes

↳ By specific individuals

– Yes [specify]: Priestly Elite (High Priest) once a year.

Is maintenance of the place performed:

– Field doesn't know

Pilgrimage and Festivals

Are pilgrimages present:

– Yes

Notes: For the purposes of sacrifice

↳ How strict is pilgrimage:

– field doesn't know

↳ Are pilgrimages the main reason for construction/establishment of the place:

– No

↳ Are pilgrimages to this place associated with significant life events:

– I don't know

↳ Does pilgrimage to this place involve following established routes (roads):

– I don't know

Is this place a venue for feasting:

– No

Are festivals present:

– I don't know

Divination and Healing

Is divination present:

– No

Is healing present/practiced at this place:

– Yes

↳ Incubation

– Yes

Do rituals occur at this place:

Rituals are visibly enacted behaviors by one or more people for the purposes of religious observance.

– Yes

↳ Do large-scale rituals take place:

– Yes

↳ Do small-scale rituals take place:

– Yes

Institutions and Scriptures

Religious Specialists

Are religious specialists present/in charge of this place:

Religious specialists are individuals whose primary duties within a population group are not concerned with subsistence or craft production but the maintenance of the religious landscape and culture of the group.

– Yes

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific sex/gender:

– Yes

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific ethnicity:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: There are several ways to answer this question. Yes, in the broadest sense the specialists (priests) are assumed to have been Hebrews and the Biblical text indicates that they were to be from the tribe of Levi. However, there is insufficient data to comment on the historical situation. In this sense, scholars debate the nature of the ambiguous phrase "priests and Levites."

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific class/cast:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are religious specialists dedicated to the place for life:

– I don't know

Does this place incorporate a living space for religious specialists:

– Yes

Notes: Difficult to say for certain because of the fuzzy nature of the data, but the text of Samuel seems to indicate that Eli and Samuel lived in the "Tabernacle" complex (though the tradition may have a different ritual tent in mind).

Is this place used for the training of religious specialists:

– Yes

Notes: Samuel is raised in the Tabernacle (1 Sam. 1-2).

Are there formal institutions for the maintenance of the place:

Institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders

– Yes

Bureaucracy

Is there a formal bureaucracy present at this place:

A bureaucracy consists of a hierarchical system of accounting and rule maintenance primarily concerned with material wealth.

– I don't know

Does this place control economic resources (land, goods, tools):

– Field doesn't know

Public Works

Does this place serve as a location for services to the community:

– I don't know

Writing/Scriptures

Is non-religious writing stored at this place:

Economic documents, records etc.

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Insufficient data to comment between the Shiloh "Tabernacle" tradition and the wilderness tradition.

Are there scriptures associated with this place:

– Yes

↳ Are they written:

– Yes

↳ Are they written at this place:

– No

↳ Are they oral:

– I don't know

↳ Is there a story associated with the origin and/or construction of this place:

– Yes

↳ Are there religious specialists in charge of interpreting the scriptures:

– Yes

↳ Are the scriptures part of the building/place:

– Yes

↳ Attached to the structures as decoration:

– No

↳ Housed within the place/structure:

– Yes

Notes: The Ark of the Covenant, a ritual object in the Tabernacle, is said to have housed the tablets of the covenant (Exod. 25:10-22).

↳ As dedicatory inscription(s):

– No

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